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IMPACT OF CURRENT TOURISM TRENDS ON THE FORMATION OF LEISURE CULTURE: UKRAINIAN CONTEXT

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The purpose of the article is to analyse the impact of current tourism trends on the formation of leisure culture. The research methodology consists of the analysis of the primary statistical and scientific sources on the impact of tourism trends on the shape of leisure culture, interdisciplinary synthesis of the main forms of actualisation of tourism trends on the localisation of tourist flows, methods of deduction and induction, as well as content analysis. Scientific novelty. The article identifies current tourism trends of our time, which will significantly shape leisure overculture. The author grounds and introduces into scientific use of the theory of cultural studies and tourism studies the concepts of “tourism trend” and “leisure culture”. Conclusions. Based on the analysis of statistical materials of the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), data from United Nations experts, the history of tourism development vectors in the context of a pandemic is summarised. The article describes and analyses current tourism trends that will impact the formation of leisure culture in the years to come. In particular, the development of domestic tourism under the condition of improving its service; the use of social networks for marketing and marketing of a tourism product; the development of internet technology, 24-7 blogging support; the development of virtual tourism, which is provided by virtual (VR) and augmented (AR) reality; 24-7 customer support chatbots (chatbots); robot staff in the system of essential tourism services (transport, accommodation and leisure services). Thus, if there is an improvement of domestic service, the current tourism trends will create an environment where we can expect Ukrainian tourism to be a significant segment of leisure culture.

Keywords: tourism trend; tourist flow; tourism destination; formation of leisure culture

Introduction

According to the forecasts, the global changes in the global economy today will significantly affect leisure culture. In the next decade, there will be significant changes in the hospitality and tourism industry, reflecting changes

in consumer values. In addition, the concepts of recreation will also be transformed, which will affect the priorities of leisure culture and, as a result, tourist and recreational activities. Therefore, tourism stakeholders, both in the private and public sectors, should consider these changes to achieve and maintain the competitive advantages of their tourism companies. All the more, changes will occur in all types of tourism in the context of new information technology. The experts predict that in the next 15 years, the world will face even more tremendous quantum leaps in information and communication technologies and other fields of science and technology (Yesawich, 2000).

Today, the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) distinguishes five main factors that support general trends/tendencies and form tourist flows, namely:

- globalisation based on long-term economic tendencies (recovery of the world economy, strengthening of globalisation processes);
- social tendencies, in particular, urbanisation, individualisation, hedonisation of recreation, aspirations and expectations of new generations;
- political tendencies, in particular, assurance of the safety of tourists, cultural experience exchange, strengthening of the national cybersecurity of countries around the world;
- environmental tendencies, in particular, energy and natural resources, climate changes, natural resource management, agricultural development and the shift to a healthy natural diet;
- the development of digital technologies (World Tourism Organization, n.d.b).

Purpose of the article

The purpose of the study is to analyse current tourism trends and ascertain their impact on the formation of the national leisure culture.

The task of the study is to analyse the most significant new tourism trends, their impact on the priorities of leisure culture, in particular, innovative forms, types and subtypes of tourism, as well as to substantiate the expediency of the use of the experience of study of various forms of the organisation of tourist trips focused on the comprehensive development of national leisure culture.

The methodological basis of the research consists of the analysis of the primary statistical and scientific sources on the impact of tourism trends on the formation of leisure culture, interdisciplinary synthesis of the main forms of actualisation of tourism trends on the localisation of tourist flows, methods of deduction and induction, as well as content analysis.

Recent research and publications analysis. The question of the current state of leisure culture in the youth environment was considered by M. Jedrzejewski (1999), focusing on tendencies of world subcultures' self-identification. P. Yesawich (2000) determined the importance of new trends for the future of tourism and their impact on leisure culture formation. O. Vyshnevskaya (2009), studying the phenomenon of tourism in modern society, proves the importance of tourism as a factor of the preservation of local identity and culture through the prism of tourist activity and the formation of national leisure culture on

this basis. The author of this article considered the socio-cultural aspects of weekend tourism and development priorities for the formation of a new format of leisure culture in previous studies (Ustymenko, 2016).

However, the main array of publications devoted to the various aspects of the functioning and formation of leisure culture concerns the traditional formats that existed until 2020. Now there arise new problems in cross-cultural communication, tourism ethics, the shape of innovative types of tourism, etc. In this context, attention should be paid to recent tourism trends that significantly affect the formation of modern leisure culture.

Main research material

The current dynamics of tourist flows in the world is conditioned on the crisis, which is a consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the new issue of the World Tourism Barometer from the United Nations specialised agency, the number of international tourist arrivals in September 2020 was 65% of 100% comparing with the previous period. It is an unprecedented decrease since most countries worldwide have closed borders and imposed travel restrictions in response to the pandemic.

According to UNWTO, the massive drop in international travel demand over January – June 2020 translates into a loss of 440 million international arrivals and about the USA \$ 460 billion in export revenues from international tourism. It is around five times the loss in international tourism receipts recorded in 2008 amid the global economic and financial crisis (UNWTO, 2020).

Despite the gradual reopening of many destinations since the second half of May, the anticipated improvement in international tourism numbers did not materialise during the peak summer season. Europe was the second-hardest hit of all global regions. The decline in tourist arrivals was 66% in the first half of 2020; the Americas (– 55%), Africa and the Middle East (both – 57%) also suffered. However, Asia and the Pacific, the first region to feel the impact of COVID-19 on tourism, was the hardest hit, with a 72% fall in tourists for the six months.

North-East Asia (83%) and Southern Mediterranean Europe (72%) suffered the largest declines at the sub-regional level. All world regions and sub-regions recorded declines of more than 50% in arrivals in January – June 2020. The contraction of international demand is also reflected in double-digit declines in global tourism expenditure. Major outbound markets such as the USA and China continue to be at a standstill, though some markets such as France and Germany have shown some improvement in June (UNWTO, n.d.a).

Making forecasts for the future, it is likely that there will be a decrease in demand for travel and consumer confidence, which will negatively affect the dynamics of tourist flows until the end of 2021. UNWTO published three scenarios in May 2020, indicating declines of 58% to 78% in international tourist arrivals in 2020. Furthermore, the current trends indicate a decline in demand by 70% in August (UNWTO, 2021).

The expansion of the scenarios till the end of 2021 indicates the possibility of gradual and linear removal of travel restrictions next year, vaccination

and restoration of travellers' confidence in their safety. However, the return to 2019 level, taking into account the number of tourist arrivals, will take from 2 to 4 years, depending on the region and the pace of overcoming the socio-economic crisis.

A key element of the success of the tourism industry is the ability to recognise changes and work with them in a wide range of behavioural, environmental and technological factors, integrating their interaction. That is, special attention should be paid to modern tourism trends. Therefore, it is necessary to define the concept of "tourism trend".

So, a tourism trend tends to change in tourism, which can be linear, systemic or cyclical.

The main tourism trends in the development of the industry should be the use of digital technologies, namely:

- 24-7 blogging support;
- voice-based information retrieval, organisation and control on the route;
- virtual tourism, provided by virtual (VR) and augmented (AR) reality;
- the increase in the share of contactless payments;
- 24-7 customer support chatbots (chatbots);
- robot staff at airports and hotels (Buhalis, 2000).

Theoretical knowledge and the ability to use it will become more important for competitive advantages in the organisation of any journey. In the future, knowledge will become an active resource in the economy and business. Those countries, companies and people who use it will do better and earn more than those who don't (Yesawich, 2000).

The COVID-19 pandemic has harmed all areas of leisure, but especially in the tourism industry. The consequences of the COVID-19 outbreak were felt by the entire tourism business in the world, losses of which are estimated at dozens of billion dollars. The World Travel & Tourism Council says up to 50 million jobs in the travel & tourism sector are at risk due to the global COVID-19 pandemic.

The tourism industry faced problems that it had never experienced so acutely before. In 2020, UN experts published disappointing statistics on the prospects for the tourism industry's recovery in the context of the crisis associated with quarantine restrictions. And in August of the same year, the UN published the Tourism and COVID-19 analytical report, in which it explained possible scenarios for the development of the situation in this market. According to the experts' forecasts, the reduction in costs will be from 1.5 trillion dollars (in 2019) to 310–570 billion in the coming years. However, another fight against the pandemic may lead to the fact that about 120 million people will be dismissed in this sector. Unfortunately, according to forecasts, the real improvements in the tourism industry in 2019 are expected only in 2023 ("To Recovery & Beyond", 2020).

Therefore, we consider it is appropriate to develop researches on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the development of domestic national tourism in Ukraine, which in its turn causes the fulfilment of the following tasks: the analysis of the publications on the topic under study; the characteristics of

the main problems and prospects for the development of tourism in Ukraine in 2021; the determination of the main directions of development of domestic tourism and strategies for the improvement of the state of affairs in the domestic tourism market.

The analysis showed that before the COVID-19 crisis, tourism in Ukraine was in a state of recovery after a significant decline associated with the political events of 2014. The most prominent tourism destinations — Kyiv, Odesa and Lviv — are the most developed in the formation of the cost of tourism services, destination management and popularity for the vast majority of international tourists and have the best chances for the accumulation of tourist flows and, therefore, profits.

The situation in Ukraine, as well as in the world in general, is quite unfavourable. During the first weeks after the introduction of quarantine, the whole tourism business was in a state of uncertainty; there were no clear instructions on how to act in this situation because there was no similar event on a global scale before. But the decision had to be made quickly. The main problem was the pause of airline activities, flight cancellations and border closures. On the first day of the quarantine, the Ukrainian low-cost carrier SkyUp reduced flights to Israel and Italy. The next day, March 12, the largest Ukrainian carrier, UIA cancelled about 2,000 flights scheduled for spring. At the beginning of the summer season, the tourism industry lost about USA 1,5 billion. There are no statistics on tourism in Ukraine as of 2020, and it will be possible to systematise the data only during 2021. The entrepreneurs of the national tourism industry could only follow the development of events because they could not influence potential tourists and make them travel during the pandemic. However, the situation with international tourism has given impetus for the development of domestic tourism.

Interestingly, mobile operators conducted their analysis of tourist flows. In particular, Vodafone Ukraine stated that this summer, the number of subscribers in southern Ukrainian resorts has significantly increased compared to the summer of 2019. Thus, in Odesa, Mykolaiv and Kherson oblasts, judging by mobile traffic growth, there were 30% more tourists than in similar periods last summer. In the Kyyrylivka resort (Zaporizhzhia oblast, the Sea of Azov), mobile traffic indicated that there arrived 55% more holidaymaker than last year. In Berdiansk (Zaporizhzhia region, the Sea of Azov), there were 37% more resort visitors than on similar dates in 2019. In the Azov resorts of the Donetsk region controlled by Kyiv, the number of people increased by 100–170%.

The most visited tourist destination was the northern Black Sea coast. Western Ukraine occupies the second place in popularity among domestic tourists after seaside resorts. The third one is the capital region and Kyiv, and the fourth one is local tourist destinations in other places, experts say. Thus, during the quarantine, the demand for domestic tourism increased. Against the background of quarantine restrictions globally, Ukrainians travelled around their country much more than in 2019. However, according to tourism experts, the reorientation of Ukrainians to domestic tourism in 2020 is a desperate move. Because, unfortunately, today our national domestic tourism does not correspond to the level offered abroad.

First, not all Ukrainian hotels and resort complexes can offer such services as most visited countries for reasonable money. Second, the service in Ukraine falls behind in almost all indicators significantly. The cost is high, and the quality, unfortunately, is mostly inappropriate. Moreover, there is little competition because there are not enough places to accommodate tourists. For example, all hotels with more or less developed infrastructure on the sea coasts of Ukraine are booked till the end of August. Another problem of the national hotel base is that sometimes it is simply impossible to monitor tourist flows since there are no precise statistics from Ukrainian hotels: partially, they work unofficially and do not pay a tourist tax, which could be used to calculate how many travellers rested at the resort and for how long (Kuchirka, 2020).

Therefore, the question of the ratio of price and service quality remains the main problem of domestic tourism. It is the main block that hinders tourism development in Ukraine because its resource potential is quite high.

According to digital tourism experts, the demand for domestic tourism in Ukraine is constantly increasing. But to recover from the crisis, tourism needs to be optimised. The main ways are to improve the service and strengthen the information and advertising campaign. On the web, one can often find information about the losses of Ukraine due to the restrictions in tourism for several billion dollars. And here, the reason is that a significant amount of cash flows are “black” in the tourism business. Due to this, it is advertising on the Internet is insufficient. And this is very important for survival today, especially for small companies. Therefore it is the crisis that will help businesses step out of the shadows (“Turyzm pislia karantynu”, 2020).

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, most travel companies have switched to a remote format of work, which requires the creation of an appropriate system for the promotion and attraction of new customers and the formation of their loyalty. Today, the most effective platforms for advertising travel products and services are Instagram and Telegram. It is predicted that the number of active users of these platforms will grow exponentially this year. That is, for the tourism business, these social networks are an excellent opportunity for promotion.

The most effective method of promotion on Instagram is advertising through opinion leaders. These are public figures who are listened to by the public. Special attention should be paid to travel bloggers. They are focused on the tourism industry and are considered industry experts, thematic specialists who have a large audience. The subscribers, including potential buyers of travel services, pay attention to their advice.

Another popular and effective method of promotion is targeting, which allows selecting only the target audience from the entire audience and showing ads to it. This approach makes it possible to make advertising more accessible and personalised. It increases the involvement of the target audience and the chances that a potential buyer or customer will purchase a tourism product. The targeted advertising also allows segmenting the target audience by interests, location, age, and other criteria. It is crucial to set it up correctly to make it viewable to the most significant number of potential customers. To do this, it

is necessary to accurately determine the target audience of a tourist company and promote its services.

Today marketing on the Instagram platform is one of the most effective for the formation of sales of tourism products and services. The promotion of the Instagram profile provides an opportunity to increase the profitability of the on-line travel business. This social network helps to become famous among many users, sell more and promote your brand. Together with subscribers, the company gets potential buyers who can form the main customer base (Buhalis, 2000).

Regarding the socio-cultural review, attention should be paid to the motivation of tourism needs, socio-cultural changes, the impact of tourism on the standard of living of tourism centres, stereotypes of tourist behaviour and the process of the establishment of contacts between tourists and the host party, that is, the conditions of contact (mentality, culture, the language of prohibition, information, traditions, etc.), the possibilities of success of positive contacts for both parties (Vyshnevskaya, 2009). If previously the tourism industry focused on the standardisation of a person, his culture and needs, now the advantage in the development of the tourism industry is given to such trends as humanisation, socialisation, greening, which are stipulated by the changes in the main priorities, which in their turn affect the motivation of human activity both in everyday life and within the tourism (Ustymenko, 2016).

Conclusion

So, the current tourism trends that affect the formation of leisure culture significantly in our time and the coming years will be the development of domestic tourism under the condition of the improvement of its service; the use of social networks for marketing and marketing of a tourism product; the development of internet technology, 24-7 blogging support; the development of virtual tourism, which is provided by virtual (VR) and augmented (AR) reality; 24-7 customer support chatbots (chatbots); robot staff in the system of basic tourism services (transport, accommodation and leisure services).

Thus, if there is an improvement of domestic service, the current tourism trends will create an environment where we can expect Ukrainian tourism to be a significant segment of leisure culture.

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ВПЛИВ СУЧАСНИХ ТУРИСТИЧНИХ ТРЕНДІВ НА ФОРМУВАННЯ ДОЗВІЛЛЕВОЇ КУЛЬТУРИ: УКРАЇНСЬКИЙ КОНТЕКСТ

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Мета роботи — проаналізувати вплив сучасних туристичних трендів на формування дозвіллевої культури. Методологія дослідження складається з аналізу основних статистичних та наукових джерел щодо впливу туристичних трендів на формування дозвіллевої культури, міждисциплінарного синтезу основних форм актуалізації туристичних трендів на локалізацію туристичних потоків, методів дедукції та індукції, контент-аналізу. Наукова новизна. Визначено актуальні туристичні тренди сучасності, які суттєво впливатимуть на формування дозвіллевої культури населення. Обґрунтовано і введено до наукового обігу теорії культурології та туризмознавства поняття «туристичний тренд» та «дозвіллева культура». Висновки.

На підставі аналізу статистичних матеріалів Всесвітньої туристичної організації (UNWTO), даних від експертів Організації Об'єднаних Націй узагальнено картину змін векторів розвитку туризму в умовах пандемії. Охарактеризовано та проаналізовано сучасні туристичні тренди, що впливатимуть на формування дозвілєвої культури в найближчі роки. Зокрема, розвиток внутрішнього туризму за умови покращення його сервісу; використання соціальних мереж для маркетингу та збуту туристичного продукту; розвиток інтернет-технологій, цілодобова блогерська підтримка; розвиток віртуального туризму, що забезпечений віртуальною (VR) та доповненою (AR) реальністю; цілодобова підтримка чат-ботами (chat-bots); роботизований персонал у системі основних туристичних послуг (транспорт, служби розміщення та дозвілля). Таким чином, сукупно сучасні туристичні тренди за умови покращення вітчизняного сервісу, створюють те середовище, в якому може очікуватися розвиток українського туризму як вагомого сегмента дозвілєвої культури.

Ключові слова: туристичний тренд; туристичний потік; туристична дестинація; формування дозвілєвої культури

ВЛИЯНИЕ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИХ ТРЕНДОВ НА ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ДОСУГОВОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ: УКРАИНСКИЙ КОНТЕКСТ

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Цель работы — проанализировать влияние современных туристических трендов на формирование досуговой культуры. Методология исследования состоит из анализа основных статистических и научных источников по влиянию туристических трендов; междисциплинарного синтеза актуализации туристических трендов на локализацию туристических потоков; методов дедукции и индукции, контент-анализа. Научная новизна. Определены актуальные туристические тренды современности, которые существенно влияют на формирование досуговой культуры населения. Обоснованы и введены в научный оборот теории культурологии и туризмоведения понятия «туристический тренд» и «досуговая культура». Выводы. На основе анализа статистических материалов Всемирной туристической организации (UNWTO), данных от экспертов Организации Объединенных Наций обобщена картина смены векторов в развитии туризма в условиях пандемии. Охарактеризованы и проанализированы основные современные туристические тренды, которые будут оказывать влияние на формирование досуговой культуры в ближайшие годы. В частности, развитие внутреннего туризма при улучшении его сервиса; использование социальных сетей для маркетинга и сбыта туристского продукта; развитие интернет-технологий; круглосуточная блогерская поддержка; развитие виртуального туризма, обеспеченного виртуальной (VR) и дополненной (AR) реальностью; круглосуточная поддержка чат-

ботами (chat-bots); роботизированный персонал в системе основных туристических услуг (транспорт, службы размещения и досуга). Таким образом, современные туристические тренды при условии улучшения отечественного сервиса совместно создают ту среду, в которой может ожидать развитие украинского туризма как весомого сегмента досуговой культуры.

Ключевые слова: туристический тренд; туристический поток; туристическая дестинация; формирование досуговой культуры